

Quantum Equilibrium Not Based on Particle Equilibrium?

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Classical statistical mechanics is based on the notion of a particle (i.e. its x and p phase space) as is Newtonian mechanics which is based on $x(t)$. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, contains particle-wave duality and is linked to Newtonian mechanics (in that one considers bound state, motion etc), but is also considered to be statistical.

In this note we consider the statistical features of quantum mechanics by examining a reflection/refraction of light problem with incident light moving along the positive x direction. If considered from the point of view of a particle (i.e. photon) (in accordance with Newtonian mechanics and classical statistical mechanics) there is no equilibrium. One may imagine one photon strike the medium at a time. This photon retains its energy, but has a certain probability “ a ” to reflect at $x=0$ and $1-a$ to refract. Thus energy and photon number are conserved, but “ a ” is unknown and the energy and particle number to the left and right of x are not the same, even if one considers a steady state stream. In other words, there is a discontinuity at $x=0$ because of the difference in energy and photon numbers, yet a steady state picture seems to imply a kind of equilibrium which is not present in the particle picture.

In other words, there should be invariance along the x axis with continuity at $x=0$, but this cannot be achieved by only considering particles (i.e. photons). Nevertheless, photons are physical and whatever solution is found must be consistent with photon energy and number conservation. This seems to suggest a new physical property needed to establish the equilibrium which somehow coexists with the particle picture. We suggest this property is wavelength with a photon being described by $\exp(ipx)$ (the square root of flux) and that it is this scenario which allows one to see the reflection/refraction problem as an equilibrium one. In other words, one does not need a particle point of view to establish equilibrium, yet particle number/energy may still be conserved in this picture.

Classical Physics and the Particle Point of View

Newtonian mechanics and classical statistical mechanics use the particle point of view to describe both $x(t)$ motion in the presence of a force and statistical equilibrium with a temperature T and a potential $V(x)$. Thus the notion of a particle is key as there is no other notion. In statistical mechanics there is the idea of a density, but it is a density of particles.

In fact, Newton considered light to consist of particle-like objects i.e. photons. Later in the early 1800s, it was shown experimentally that interference of light exists, so there was a shift of thinking and light was considered to be strictly a wave until 1905 when Einstein showed that the photoelectric effect indicated that light energy was not spread out over a wave, but rather p impulses were delivered. Thus a dual nature of light seemed to exist.

It is interesting to note that a basic experiment which exists in the classical world, i.e. the reflection/refraction of light, seems to link the notion of a light wave with equilibrium, while being consistent with a particle (i.e. photon) picture which cannot describe such an equilibrium. We consider this in the next sections.

Reflection/Refraction of Light

Consider the problem of light moving in the positive x direction striking a medium along the y axis at $x=0$. Some light will reflect and the rest will refract. In fact, one may apply this picture to a single photon which has a probability “a” to reflect and $1-a$ to refract. This seems to lead to two pictures.

Picture A

One has a single photon which reaches the medium interface at $x=0$ and either reflects or refracts. The photon number is conserved as is its energy, but there is no equilibrium along the x axis because translational symmetry is broken. There is only a probability $1-a$ for a photon to continue along $x>0$ and a probability “a” for it to reflect. Thus there are different numbers of photons to the left and right of $x=0$ if one sends in a set of photons.

Picture B

One may consider a steady stream of photons (i.e a steady state scenario). This has the semblance of an equilibrium picture, but again if one thinks in terms of photon numbers and energies, there are more photons and more energy on the left hand side than on the right. As a result, this does not seem like an equilibrium scenario with translational invariance and continuity at $x=0$. As in (1), one may write conservation of energy in terms of fluxes/intensities in the problem with intensity of beam A written as $AA = n_1 E c_1$ where n_1 is the number of photons, E the energy of a photon and c_1 its speed. AA is used to show that intensity is strictly positive. Then:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

A represents the incident beam, B the reflected and C the refracted. C_1 has the same magnitude for the incident and reflected beam, but the refracted has c_2 according to $E=pc$. ((1)) represents both conservation of energy and particle number. It is arranged in terms of time i.e. is consistent with the picture of a single photon (part of A) coming in and either reflecting or refracting.

There are at least four important points associated with ((1)). First, intensity is not conserved, rather there is conservation of photon number and energy. Secondly, the equation is displayed in terms of time with the LHS being the “before time” and the RHS side the “after time”. Thirdly, the single equation ((1)) cannot be used to solve for the two unknowns B and C in terms of A. Finally, there seems to be no sense of equilibrium. The conservation equation ((1)) already holds for a single photon.

The problem is that even though a particle analysis of this problem does not lead to an equilibrium picture and continuity at $x=0$, the notion of a steady stream seems to suggest a kind of equilibrium picture. Thus unlike classical statistical mechanics, it seems one cannot use the

Newtonian picture of a particle to describe an equilibrium in this scenario. At the same time, the photon (particle) is real and cannot be discarded. It moves like a particle with speed $x=ct$.

Introducing a Wave Scenario to Establish Equilibrium

In an earlier note (2) we argued that ((1)) may be broken into two equations using the notion of a difference of squares.i.e.

$$A+B=C \text{ ((2a)) and } pA - pB = p^2C \text{ ((2b))}$$

This “splitting process”, however, is not unique. One could also write:

$$\sqrt{p}A + \sqrt{p}B = \sqrt{p^2} C \text{ ((3a)) and } \sqrt{p}A - \sqrt{p}B = \sqrt{p^2}C \text{ ((3c))}$$

This leads to the unusual result of $B=0$ and $A= \sqrt{p^2}/\sqrt{p} C$. For $n_1 < n_2$, $c_1 > c_2$ and $p < p^2$ for E to be constant, so A is less than C which is unphysical. Nevertheless, one may create a variety of difference of squares equations e.g. $\sqrt{p}/b A + b\sqrt{p}B = \sqrt{p^2}C$ and $b\sqrt{p}A - \sqrt{p}/b B = \sqrt{p^2}C$ etc. Thus there is not one unique way of writing a difference of squares.

An immediate question is: Why would one take the square root of intensity in the first place? This seems to involve moving away from a particle picture which classically is the only picture. One may answer mathematically stating that two equations are needed to solve for two unknowns B and C , but that is not a physical answer. Furthermore, the mathematical solutions which allow for different differences of squares scenarios don't seem to consider a kind of steady state equilibrium and are not unique. If such an equilibrium exists (and this chooses the form of the differences of squares), what is a key feature of it? It seems one wishes to have some kind of translational invariance which does not appear in the particle picture. The square root approach ((2a)), ((2b)) is promising if it may be linked to a kind of continuous flow/equilibrium picture i.e. continuity at $x=0$.

The generator for translations is d/dx and $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ (as well as d/dx linked to kinetic energy). The magnitude of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 which links it to a constant intensity. $\exp(ipx)$ describes a kind of wave scenario with two components. What kind of wave is this? The notion of a particle must still exist and the square of $\exp(ipx)$ (object time complex conjugate) gives the flux, thus it seems that $\exp(ipx)$, which depends on the particle property p , may describe a kind of position probability. Thus we do not take \sqrt{p} etc in the difference of squares approach, but use p which follows from $-id/dx$.

It is this position/dynamical type of probability which allows one to consider the reflection/refraction problem as an equilibrium with continuity at $x=0$. This, however, violates the notion of $x=ct$ which holds for a photon for all x and t . Thus $\exp(ipx)$ seems to introduce a physical wavelength \hbar/p in which $x=vt$ motion only occurs on average, but in which the particle may appear at different x points with a probability of $\cos(px)$. This is added to $i \sin(px)$ to ensure an modulus of 1. In such an approach, one may establish equilibrium and continuity at $x=0$ i.e.

$$A+B = C \quad \text{and} \quad pA - pB = p_2C$$

with the idea that one really has $A\exp(ipx)$, $B\exp(-ipx)$ and $C\exp(ip_2x)$. A main feature of the wave type approach is that it accounts for B dampening A in the case of $n_1 < n_2$. A phase of 3.14 i.e. $\exp(i 3.14) = -1$ leads to B being negative and dampening A so that $A+B$ is continuous with C at $x=0$. Thus we see the idea of a particle at work in $\exp(ipx)$, but at the same time the notion of interference which is more important. For example, if one considers $\cos(px)$ alone then there is a peak at $\cos(px)=1$ and a trough peak at $\cos(px)=-1$. If one squares (as $\cos(px)$ is the square root flux) one has 1 and 1 i.e. the particle has equal probability to be at either point and this is a maximum probability. If one adds the square root fluxes, however, a negative peak cancels with a positive one and so one may reduce the overall value. Thus interference may shift the probabilities of the particle along the x axis, although the notion of a particle does not disappear.

As a result, if one thinks of the problem spatially, then the LHS contains incident and reflected particles. These have energy and particle number which add. Thus there is no way for the particle view to lead to $A+B$ being less than A. The square root flux/intensity $\exp(ipx)$ approach, however, through phase shifts allows for such a feature which is necessary to have continuity with C and hence a kind of equilibrium.

Is the Notion of Equilibrium More Fundamental than the Notion of a Particle?

The reflection/refraction problem seems to show that if one only considers the notion of a particle, i.e. one photon entering at a time then there is no equilibrium scenario and no solution for the probabilities for a photon to reflect or refract. The solution for probabilities seems to be dependent on the notion of an equilibrium and this equilibrium in turn leads to very non-particle-like behaviour i.e. the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ probability type waves or square root fluxes/intensities. The very notion of $\cos(px)$ contradicts $x=ct$ so the latter may only be an average property. The wave picture, however, allows for the establishment of continuity at $x=0$. Thus it is the driving scenario and must also be physical i.e. \hbar/p the wavelength is a physical phenomenon. The notion of a particle, however, cannot simply disappear. In fact, $\exp(ipx)$ depends on p which is a particle property. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ must establish the "particle" feature in the problem which is conservation of energy/particle number, but this is not an equilibrium feature. As a result, using $A\exp(ipx)$ as a square root flux allows for one to create equilibrium and solve for B and C:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) \text{ vs } C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{and} \quad pA\exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx)B \text{ vs } Cp_2 \exp(ip_2x)$$

At $x=0$ and $\rightarrow pAA - pBB = CCp_2$ which is conservation of energy/particle number.

Thus dynamics i.e. equilibrium seem to be more fundamental than only the consideration of energy/photon number conservation.

Particle with Rest Mass

The above ideas may be extended to a particle with rest mass. One may consider a potential $V(x)$ in a region near $x=0$ which dies down quickly (or a hard sphere) and $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$ near $x=-\infty$ and $C\exp(ipx)$ near $x=\infty$ as well as the corresponding momentum equation. In this case p is the same throughout and one has a conservation of intensity, but it is still the square root flux $\exp(ipx)$ form which establishes equilibrium and allows for one to solve for the two unknowns B, C in terms of A .

Special Relativity

The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ may be used to establish an internal clock with frequency \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p . One may also find that $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$ the translation generator. Using this generator, however, again suggests a kind of translational invariance which could be associated with a kind of equilibrium scenario through imposing the continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ or sums of various $\exp(ipx)$'s. Thus, using special relativity seems to be consistent with the equilibrium approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of equilibrium which appears in classical statistical mechanics is important, but need not depend on a particle view as it does in the classical world. In fact, a phenomenon which appears in the classical world, i.e. the reflection/refraction of light demonstrates this point. If one considers a single photon moving in the positive x direction, then it either reflects or refracts with probabilities " a " and $1-a$. There is seemingly no equilibrium as the " a " and $1-a$ are not equal, suggesting different numbers of photons with the same energy on either side of $x=0$ (if the medium is along the y axis at $x=0$). An alternative picture is to consider flux/intensity i.e. a steady stream of photons, but if there is no equilibrium for one photon, there is no intensity equilibrium either. In fact, the intensity may be written as part of a conservation of energy equation i.e. $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ ((MM)) (where A, B, C refer to the incident, reflected and refracted beams).

The idea we suggest is that energy/particle number conservation leads to only one equation, but there are two unknowns B, C in terms of A . Thus we suggest that the notion of equilibrium is a fundamental idea in the problem, but cannot be expressed in terms of particles. This is completely at odds with classical statistical mechanics. In fact, we suggest that one may use ((MM)), write it as a difference of squares and obtain two equations allowing one to solve for B and C . The problem is that this difference of squares set is not unique, leading to different solutions. Thus there must be a physical idea leading to the one correct solution. We suggest this is the idea of equilibrium, albeit at a square root flux level and not at a particle level. The particle view only includes conservation of energy/photon number. Thus the square root flux level must create an equilibrium scenario with continuity at $x=0$, but at the same preserve particle number/energy conservation. This means a break with the particle equation $x=ct$. In fact, in order to have a kind of spatial invariance (linked to continuity at $x=0$) we examine the

generator of translations d/dx . $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ and maps into 1 i.e. $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ which represents steady flux. The form $\exp(ipx)$, however, allows for interference which is key to establishing equilibrium/continuity at x . For example, if one considers $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$ then a phase from $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\exp(-i3.14)$ yields -1 which allows for B to diminish A until it equals C i.e. $A+B=C$ at $x=0$. The crest and trough in $\cos(px)$ represent the same particle peak probability if one squares, but given the difference in sign, the wave form may shift the particle probability from one x to another.

Thus we argue that equilibrium is a key notion in nature and may be achieved without using a particle view (i.e the only view in classical statistical mechanics). An example which exists in the classical world, i.e. the reflection/refraction of light, shows that a particle view cannot go further than a conservation equation, but an equilibrium created by a square root flux (wave type probability which may interfere, but whose magnitude restores the particle type picture) can account for the reflected and refracted probabilities.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change

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